

"INNOVATIVE ACHIEVEMENTS IN SCIENCE 2022"

WOMEN'S PROTECTION IN UZBEKISTAN: REAL OR MYTH?

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Introduction :*In recent years, the attention to women's rights has significantly increased. Governmental and societal changes have been introduced. National Human Rights Strategy¹⁰ was approved in June 2020 to protect and promote human rights in the country. The new regulations laws "On protecting women from oppression and violence"¹¹ and "On guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men"¹² have been adopted. However, there are serious issues relating to women's rights in Uzbekistan. According to research conducted by the United States Agency for International Development (USAID), the main barriers to releasing women's rights in the states are the wording of laws and enforcement of them, limited access to justice in cases of violence against women and society's thinking.¹³*

Gaps in legislation : *In recent years changes to the current laws have been introduced and the Women's Committee was created to help vulnerable women. However, still, domestic violence is not criminalized.*

There is no provision in the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan on domestic violence. It should be highlighted that domestic violence is one of the crucial issues in Uzbekistan. For a couple of years, the headlines were full of cases of domestic violence, but still, there is no criminal liability for such crime. Protection orders are introduced, but there is no result from them as it is expected. *Nemolchi.uz* is an independent information project against violence in Uzbekistan. Every day many stories of real women are posted on this platform. A man seriously injured his wife, and as the result, she had a traumatic brain injury, beatings, bruises and other serious health injuries. She obtained the protection order but it did not stop the abuser. When she called a local police officer, he did not try to help

¹⁰ Ukaz Prezidenta Respubliki Uzbekistan "Ob utverjdenii nacionalnoy strategii Respubliki Uzbekistan po pravam cheloveka" UP-6012 ot 22.06.2020.

¹¹ Zakon Respubliki Uzbekistan "O zashite jenshin ot pritesneniya i nasiliya" ZRU-561 ot 03.09.2019.

¹² Zakon Respubliki Uzbekistan "O gatantiyax ravnix prav i vozmojnostey dlya jenshin i mujchin" ZRU-562 ot 03.09.2019.

¹³ USAID, "Results of the Research: Improving Gender Legislation: National Experience and International Practice" (2022).

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and did not pay attention to the woman's words. Such situations are common in this country and accepted as the norm since it is between husband and wife and family is holy. This case shows that the legislation might say one thing, however, the reality is absolutely different.

Another serious issue is rape. In many cases when 13 years old girl gets pregnant or is forced to have a sexual relationship with one of her family members, brothers, cousins, or even fathers is classified as sexual acts with minors, not rape. However, a sexual act between 13 years old kid and a more than 30 years old man must fall under rape. Unfortunately, such cases are not classified as rape but as the sexual act with mutual consent article 128 of the Criminal Code. The maximum punishment is 3 years for the rape of a kid. In the eye of Uzbek law, it is not raping it is mutual consent even though girls were forced or lured. A 31 years old man raped 14 years old girl and started blackmailing the girl to tell everyone if she stops visiting him. In Uzbekistan having a sexual act before the wedding is shameful and under such intimidation, she continued visiting him but could not stand it any longer and told mom. Supreme court held that a sexual act under blackmailing which started from rape is not rape, it is a sexual act with a minor and sentenced rapist to 3 years. This shows that the law does not protect women and that "changes" are not real.

The following issue is harassment. Harassment is a serious crime in many developed countries but not in Uzbekistan. There is no term "harassment" in the administrative or criminal code. Such action is usually classified as petty hooliganism. There is no specific law on such crime.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

There are positive movements toward the protection of women, however, they are not enough. Practice shows that the main issues such as protection from domestic violence, rape and harassment which are crucial for every woman are overlooked. Therefore, the following changes shall be introduced to provide real protection and equality to women:

- Include a definition of domestic violence into the Criminal Code;
- Amend the definition of rape and other sexual offences to take into account the circumstances of the case not only the absence of involuntary consent;
- Amend article 128 of the Criminal Code and classify sexual act with a minor as rape;
- Remove community service and correctional labour for sexual offences;

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- Include the definition of harassment into laws and impose criminal liability.